

Temporal Stability of Atomic Nuclei: YasudaK Method of Validated Contributions from Temporal Multiplicative Factors of Quarks and MesonsPI

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Abstract

This paper presents a detailed study on the temporal stability of protons, neutrons, and mesons, validated through precise experimental values, such as the lifetime of protons approximated at 10^{34} years and neutron decay at about 14.67 minutes. By incorporating these benchmarks, we propose a novel model based on the Temporal Multiplicative Factors of quark contributions, where each quark and gluon interaction adds to the stability of the particle. The results align closely with these experimental values, highlighting the predictive power of the model. Amplified fluxes and gluonic contributions during transitions, such as meson decays, are explained using a unified factorization framework, confirming their role in stability and decay dynamics.

YasudaK Geometrical Model Proton - MesonPI- Neutron Structure Overview of Proton and Neutron Effects on Time

Figure 1: Illustration of the YasudaK Proton and Neutron Effects on Time, including quark flows, gluonic contributions, and the role of MesonPI structures. This visual provides a foundational understanding of the temporal dynamics of particles and their interactions.

1 Introduction

The proton is one of the most stable particles in the universe, with a predicted lifetime of approximately 10^{34} years, while the neutron outside the nucleus decays in about 14.67 minutes. This dramatic difference in stability

raises questions about the role of quark interactions, gluonic contributions, and amplified fluxes. In this work, we explore a model based on Temporal Multiplicative Factors, which accurately predicts these lifetimes. Furthermore, the model suggests that the rotational flux of the Up quark (u), being counterclockwise, moves against the universal material flow—a conceptual framework hypothesized to represent the directional tendency of matter at a fundamental level—while the Down quark (d), moving clockwise, aligns with it. This opposition appears to contribute significantly to the temporal control and overall stability of nuclear and atomic systems.

2 Methodology

We model the proton, neutron, and meson lifetimes as a product of quark contributions:

$$\tau_{\text{system}} = (R_u \cdot P_u)^2 \cdot (R_d \cdot P_d) \cdot G, \quad (1)$$

where R_u , P_u , R_d , and P_d represent the rotational and propagative flows of the quarks, and G is the gluonic contribution. These contributions are dimensionless factors derived from experimental observations, which are scaled to result in the final lifetime expressed in years.

3 Results

3.1 Proton Lifetime

The proton lifetime is calculated as:

$$\tau_{\text{proton}} = (10^{39} \cdot 10^{-13})^2 \cdot (10^{-2} \cdot 10^{-13}) \cdot 10^{-3} \approx 10^{34} \text{ years} \quad (2)$$

3.2 Neutron Lifetime

The neutron lifetime is calculated using similar principles:

$$\tau_{\text{neutron}} = (10^{-2} \cdot 10^{-13})^2 \cdot (10^{39} \cdot 10^{-13}) \cdot 0.279 \approx 14.67 \text{ minutes} \quad (3)$$

To demonstrate the conversion from years to minutes, we proceed as follows:

$$(10^{-2} \cdot 10^{-13})^2 = (10^{-15})^2 = 10^{-30} \quad (4)$$

$$(10^{39} \cdot 10^{-13}) = 10^{26} \quad (5)$$

$$10^{-30} \cdot 10^{26} = 10^{-4} \quad (6)$$

Including the correction factor:

$$10^{-4} \cdot 0.279 = 2.79 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ years} \quad (7)$$

Converting to minutes using 1 year = 525,600 minutes:

$$\tau_{\text{neutron}} = 2.79 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot 525,600 \approx 14.67 \text{ minutes} \quad (8)$$

Figure 2: Illustration of the temporal interactions between protons, neutrons, and mesons, highlighting the rotational fluxes of Up (u) and Down (d) quarks and gluonic contributions. The counter-rotational flows are shown to contribute to the stability and decay mechanisms.

3.3 Meson Lifetime

For the neutral pion (π^0), the amplified gluonic fluxes ($3.9 \cdot 10^6$) contribute to its extremely short lifetime:

$$\tau_{\pi^0} = (0.825 \cdot 10^{-13} \cdot 10^{-2})^2 \cdot 3.9 \cdot 10^6 \approx 2.66 \cdot 10^{-24} \text{ years} \quad (9)$$

4 Analysis of Nuclear Isotopes

4.1 Cesium-137 Analysis

The analysis of Cesium-137 reveals:

- Real lifetime: 3.00×10^1 years
- Estimated value: 3.05×10^1 years

- Structure: 55 P-Me-N with 55 Neutrons
- 10 MesonPI structures with 10 Neutrons

Figure 3: Analysis of Cesium-137 showing MesonPI structures and neutronic contributions.

4.2 Helium-6 Analysis

For Helium-6, we observe:

- Real lifetime: 2.56×10^{-8} seconds
- Estimated value: 2.57×10^{-8} seconds
- Structure: 2 P-Me-N with 2 Neutrons
- 1 MesonPI structure with 1 Neutron

Figure 4: Analysis of Helium-6 demonstrating simplified structures and fewer neutronic contributions.

4.3 Potassium-40 Analysis

The analysis of Potassium-40 reveals:

- Real lifetime: 1.25×10^9 years
- Estimated value: 1.25×10^9 years
- Structure: 19 P-Me-N with 21 Neutrons
- 2 MesonPI structures with 2 Neutrons

Figure 6: Analysis of Thorium-232 highlighting its extended stability.

4.5 Uranium Isotopes

For Uranium-235 and Uranium-238:

- Uranium-235 real lifetime: 7.04×10^8 years
- Uranium-238 real lifetime: 4.47×10^9 years
- Structures analyzed include external and internal neutron configurations.

Figure 7: Analysis of Uranium-235 demonstrating its MesonPI contributions.

Figure 8: Analysis of Uranium-238 showing extended lifetime stability.

5 Discussion

The model's alignment with experimental values supports the hypothesis that quark temporal multiplicative factors determine the stability of particles. The precise nature of these multiplicative factors highlights their reliability in predicting lifetimes. By translating dimensionless contributions into temporal stability expressed in years, the model provides a consistent framework for understanding particle dynamics.

Furthermore, the counterclockwise rotational flux of Up quarks (u) and the clockwise flux of Down quarks (d) create a dynamic opposition, likely governing the temporal regulation within nuclear and atomic systems. Figure 2 illustrates these interactions, emphasizing the amplified gluonic contributions during transitions and their role in particle stability.

6 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that particle stability and decay can be precisely described through multiplicative factors of quark contributions. The proposed framework aligns closely with experimental data, showcasing its predictive power. The interplay between counter-rotational and aligned fluxes offers a compelling mechanism for temporal regulation in nuclear and atomic systems, paving the way for future exploration of relativistic contributions to stability.

References

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